

ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION AT COCA COLA PRIVATE LIMITED, HYDERABAD

Author: Dr Kavitha Maduri

Associate professor

Saanvi PG College for women, Almasguda, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

ABSTRACT:

Job satisfaction refers to one's feelings towards one's job. If the employees expectations are fulfilled (or) the employees get higher than what he / she feels satisfied. If the job satisfaction increases organization commitment will increased. This results in the higher productivity. The main objectives of this paper are to assess the job satisfaction: to identify the effectiveness of job satisfaction and to find out the several factors like personal and organizational factors influencing job satisfaction: to identify the effectiveness of job satisfaction and to find out the several factors like personal and organizational factors influencing job satisfaction of employees.

In this study, 125 no's of respondents have been taken as sample. Percentage analysis, weighted average, chi-square have been incorporated for research analysis. The study helped in revealing the level of satisfaction of employees with reference to the various factors provided in the organization. This study clearly shows that employees under organization are more or less satisfied with the job. The organization should consider on the salary, relationship of employees and supervisors, grievance handling and give more opportunity for the new employees.

Key words: job satisfaction, productivity, organizational commitment.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their job, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components Researchers have also noted that job satisfaction measures vary in the extent to which they measure feelings about the job (affective job satisfaction). or cognitions about the job (cognitive job satisfaction).The assessment of job satisfaction through employee anonymous surveys became commonplace in the 1930s.

Although prior to that time there was the beginning of interest in employee attitudes, there were only a handful of studies published. Latham and Budworth note that Uhrbrock in 1934 was one of the first psychologists to use the newly developed attitude measurement techniques to assess factory worker attitudes. They also note that in 1935 Hoppock conducted a study that focused explicitly on job satisfaction that is affected by both the nature of the job and relationships with coworkers and supervisors.

Models of job satisfaction

Edwin A. Locke's Range of Affect Theory (1976) is arguably the most famous job satisfaction model. The main premise of this theory is that satisfaction is determined by a discrepancy between what one wants in a job and what one has in a job. Further, the theory states that how much one values a given facet of work (e.g. the degree of autonomy in a position) moderates how satisfied/dissatisfied one becomes when expectations are/aren't met. When a person values a particular facet of a job, his satisfaction is more greatly impacted both positively (when expectations are met) and negatively (when expectations are not met), compared to one who doesn't value that facet. To illustrate, if Employee A values autonomy in the workplace and Employee B is indifferent about autonomy, then Employee A would be more satisfied in a position that offers a high degree of autonomy and less satisfied in a position with little or no autonomy compared to Employee B. This theory also states that too much of a particular facet will produce stronger feelings of dissatisfaction the more a worker values that facet.

1.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY:

Job satisfaction of the employees is important if the employees are satisfied then only the organization can function smoothly increases its production, faces competition. If employees are satisfied with their job they will carry a positive attitude. Hence the study has been undertaken to assess the employee job satisfaction which is necessary for the organization in order to make sound decisions. It is said that satisfied employee is a productive employee, any kind of grievance relating to organizational or personal to a greater extent influence on the job. so every organization is giving higher priority to keep their employees satisfaction by providing several facilities which improves satisfaction and which reduces dissatisfaction. Job satisfaction is considered as a key issue by the entrepreneur where efforts are taken and programs are initiated.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on their job. It is different from

person to person. The researcher has chosen to measure the level of job satisfaction in COCA COLA. The study considers only the perceptual elements of employees and does not focus on ground realities. The scope of study cover: work conditions, compensation, extra benefits, conveyance treatment of superiors, colleagues, duly timings, grievance redresal mechanism and promotion policy.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Broad objective:-

- i. To study the overall job satisfaction of employees in COCA COLA,
- ii. To measure the level of satisfaction among employees in COCA COLA
- iii. To measure the relationship and human relations & job satisfaction.
- iv. To find out the most distaining factors which influence their performance in the job. To give amicable and practical suggestions to improve job satisfaction of employees in COCA COLA.
- v. To study the growth opportunity programmers & Training programmers in notice confectionery limited.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology that is adopted for the study is such that it facilities the data accumulation. The information is gathered through survey method. The survey method has been adopted for collecting the data from employees.

DATA SOURCES:

Data means a collection of facts in real life statistical data is a collection of facts in numerical figures. The data sources are usually identified using the type of data needed. There are two types of data. The data collected for this research has provided the base for its analysis and interpretation. The data collected was used to draft charts, illustrate through graphs and thus provide for its adequate interpretation. In this research, Primary data as well as Secondary data has been used.

1. Primary data:

The primary data was collected from the respondents by administering a structured questionnaire and also through observation, interview and discussion with management.

2. Secondary data:

Company profiles, previous year report, Literatures, Journals, Internet, Intranet.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Design is defined as the specification of methods and procedures for acquiring the information needed. Generally the research design is any of the following three types-

- **DESCRIPTIVE STUDY:**

Descriptive study/research is marked by the prior formulations of specific research questions. The investigator already knows a substantial amount about the research problem before the project is initiated. Hence this is chosen for my research.

- **EXPLORATORY STUDY:**

The major purpose of exploratory study is the identification of problem, the more precision formulation of problem and the formulation of new alternative courses of action.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Broad objective:-

To study the overall job satisfaction of supervisors in COCA COLA,

Specific objectives:-

- i. To measure the level of satisfaction among supervisors in COCA COLA
- ii. To measure the relationship and human relations & job satisfaction.
- iii. To find out the most distaining factors which influence their performance in the job.
- iv. To give amicable and practical suggestions to improve job satisfaction of supervisors in COCA COLA.
- v. To study the growth opportunity programmers & Training programmers in notice confectionery limited.

CASUAL STUDY:

The study involves the determination of the causes of what the researchers are predicting. This is mainly a cause and effect study.

The research design selected by the researcher in the present study is “DESCRIPTIVE” in nature.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT:

HR research has a one main research instruments in collecting primary data. That is questionnaires.

In order to extract first-hand information from the respondents, a pre-tested questionnaire was prepared and the same was administered to the respondents.

LIMITATIONS

It is true to highlight that every research has its own limitations whether it is being conducted in any area of studies including social sciences. It might be because researcher could not possibly bring the whole perspective of a particular area in one fine study. Therefore, it is imperative to emphasize that research itself is a learning process by which researcher tries to prove many conceptual and methodological issues pertaining to his/her research work.

Hence, like other researches the present research endeavour also suffers from some of the limitations, which are enumerated below:

- i. The size of the sample of present investigation is limited in its nature, which puts a limitation on the generalization of results of the present study.
- ii. The present investigation was confined with only few Psychological variables—namely, School Organizational Climate, Teaching Attitude, Adjustment and Job Satisfaction while other important psychological variables could also have been included, such as job commitment, job involvement, job motivation, interest and others.

Models of job satisfaction

Affect Theory

Edwin A. Locke's Range of Affect Theory (1976) is arguably the most famous job satisfaction model. The main premise of this theory is that satisfaction is determined by a discrepancy between what one wants in a job and what one has in a job. When a person values a particular facet of a job, his satisfaction is more greatly impacted both positively and negatively, compared to one who doesn't value that facet. To illustrate, if Employee A values autonomy in the workplace and Employee B is indifferent about autonomy, then Employee A would be more satisfied in a position that offers a high degree of autonomy and less satisfied in a position with little or no autonomy compared to Employee B. This theory also states that too much of a particular facet will produce stronger feelings of dissatisfaction the more a worker values that facet.

Dispositional Theory

Another well-known job satisfaction theory is the Dispositional Theory Template: Jackson April 2007. It is a very general theory that suggests that people have innate dispositions that cause them to have tendencies toward a certain level of satisfaction, regardless of one's job. This approach became a notable explanation of job satisfaction in light of evidence that job satisfaction tends to be stable over time and across careers and jobs. Research also indicates that identical twins have similar levels of job satisfaction.

Two-Factor Theory (Motivator-Hygiene Theory)

Frederick Herzberg's two factor theory (also known as Motivator Hygiene Theory) attempts to explain satisfaction and motivation in the workplace this theory states that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors – motivation and hygiene factors, respectively. An employee's motivation to work is continually related to job satisfaction of a subordinate. Motivation can be seen as an inner force that drives individuals to attain personal and organizational goals (Hokinson, Porter, & Wrench, p. 133). Motivating factors are those

aspects of the job that make people want to perform, and provide people with satisfaction, for example achievement in work, recognition, promotion opportunities. Hygiene factors include aspects of the working environment such as pay, company policies, supervisory practices, and other working conditions.

3.1 INDUSTRY PROFILE

As one of the most important industries that satisfy daily human necessities, food and beverage has witnessed a surge in market share minute by minute. For a long time, they have been considered a first-rate field for running a business. Thereby, especially in the beverage industry, more and more stakeholders desire to engage in this fat land of benefit.

This article will give you a brief overview of the beverage industry: information about the general development of this giant industry- beverage segment with collected statistics, features, and the competitive level.

3.2 COMPANY PROFILE

As the largest beverage company with the most extensive distribution system in the world. You may know us simply as Coca-Cola--the world's most valuable brand and a global icon.

The Coca-Cola Company is the world's leading manufacturer, marketer, and distributor of nonalcoholic beverage concentrates and syrups. Its world headquarters is based in Atlanta, Georgia. The company and its subsidiaries employ nearly 31,000 people around the world.

The Coca-Cola Company manufactures syrups, concentrates and beverage bases for Coca-Cola, the company's flagship brand, and also produces over 230 other soft-drink brands sold by and its subsidiaries in nearly 200 countries around the world. Some of Coca-Cola's latest domestic marketing strategies include Coke dominating fountain sales. Thousands of consumers visit fast-food restaurants every day and Coke feels that it is very important to have the consumer see and drink their product at such chains as McDonalds, Burger King, and Domino's Pizza. Coca-Cola is also testing a new plastic cup in the famous Coca-Cola.

The Coca-Cola Company was first established in 1886 by Dr John Styth Pemberton. Today, the company is the world's leading manufacturer in the beverage industry, operating globally in more than 200 countries with its head office located in Atlanta, USA.

HISTORY OF COCA COLA

A pharmacist named Dr. John Stith Pemberton invented the refreshing taste of Coca-Cola in 1886. Concocted by a mixture of caramel-colored syrup in a three-legged brass kettle while in his backyard. He then decided to try to "market" the drink at Jacobs' Pharmacy in his hometown of Atlanta, Georgia. For five-cents, customers were able to enjoy a glass from the soda fountain. An average of nine drinks were sold a day. In 1891 Dr. John Stith Pemberton sold Coca-Cola for 2,300 to an entrepreneur named Asa G. Candler. Within four years Coca-Cola was distributed throughout the whole nation. 1893 the Cola-

cola trademark and script were patented. The “two C’s were though to look well for advertising”. In 1899 large-scale bottling becomes possible when Asa Candler grants Joseph B. Whitehead and Benjamin F. Thomas exclusive rights for one dollar. But in 1919 Coca-Cola was sold for \$25million to a banker in Atlanta name Ernest Woodruff and a group of investors. That same year, Coca-Cola sold its first share of stock for forty dollars a share. Assuming all dividends were reinvested, those original shares would have been worth approximately \$6.7 million at the end of the year.

Financial Performance

It discusses the most recent financials of the company and also compares the historical sales & income figures with the current and projected figures. The objective is to evaluate the financial health of the company. The analyst opinion and stock performance help us in evaluating the performance of the company from an investor’s viewpoint.

Competition Synopsis

This section compares the company with its peer group. The comparable analysis and stock movement are aimed at giving an overview of the competitive landscape in the industry and the company’s positioning in its peer group.

Analysis Soft Drink

I Analysis of the U.S. soft drink industry, based on the competitive forces model of Michael Porter.

In the soft drink industry the entry of new competitors depends on the barriers to entry that are present, and also the reaction from existing competitors that the entrant can expect.

I will now analyze the six major sources of barriers to entry the soft drink industry.

Economies of scale deter entry by forcing the entrant to come in at large scale and risk strong reaction from existing firms or come in at a small scale and accept a cost disadvantage. If a company wants to decline its unit costs of their product, they will have to produce more to lower the cost. The more you produce, the lower the costs.

Definition of soft drinks

The Coca-Cola Company North America offices in Sugar Land, Texas, United States According to the 2005 Annual Report, the company sells beverage products in more than 200 countries. The report further states that of the more than 50 billion beverage servings of all types consumed worldwide every day, beverages bearing the trademarks owned by or licensed to Coca-Cola account for approximately 1.5 billion.

Also according to the 2007 Annual Report, Coca-Cola had gallon sales distributed as follows:

- 37% in the United States

- 43% in Mexico, Brazil, Japan and the People's Republic of China
- 20% spread throughout the rest of the world

In 2010 it was announced that Coca-Cola had become the first brand to top £1 billion in annual UK grocery sales.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table No: 4.1

Working hours are convenient for you

PARTICULARS	No of responses	PERCENT
Strongly agree	17	34
Agree	16	32
Neither agree nor disagree	9	18
Disagree	6	12
Strongly disagree	2	4
TOTAL	50	100

CHART 4.1

Interpretation:

From the above chart and table it is clearly evident that 34% of the Respondents strongly agree that working hours are convenient from them and 32% agree with that and 18% neither agree nor disagree and 12% disagree with the working hours and 4% are strongly against working hours.

Table No: 4.2

Are happy with your work place

PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONSES	PERCENT
Strongly agree	15	30
Agree	20	40

Neither agree nor disagree	9	18
Disagree	4	8
Strongly disagree	2	4
TOTAL	50	100

CHART4.2

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that 30% respondents strongly agree and 40% respondents agree that they are happy with their work place only 8% disagreed and 18% have no idea towards their work place.

Table No: 4.3

Do you feel you have too much work to do

PARTICULARS	NO OF RESPONSES	PERCENT
strongly agree	4	8
Agree	4	8
Neither agree nor disagree	12	24
Disagree	19	38
Strongly disagree	11	22
	50	100

CHART-4.3

Interpretation:

From the above table it is quite clear that the work load is not high, 38% of the respondents disagreed with the question” I feel I have too much work” and another 22% strongly disagreed, 16% admits they have too much work and 24% have no idea towards this question.

FINDINGS

➤ Using the calculated Simple percentage values for the variables, the level of satisfaction of the employees in the organization can be known. They are from 100 - 80% can be regarded as Highly Satisfied, 79 - 60 % can be regarded as Satisfied , 59 - 40 % can be Regarded as neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 39 - 20 % can be regarded as Dissatisfied and 19- 0 % can be regarded as Highly Dissatisfied.

- Employees are highly satisfied with company, work and relationship with colleagues
- Experience and satisfaction with Promotional Opportunities & Possibility of Growth
- Experience and satisfaction with Training & Development

SUGGESTIONS

- There is some dissatisfaction level regarding the Salary among the employees. So, the company may conduct a further survey to find the expectations of employees.
- The study shows that employees are not satisfied with the working environment and infrastructure. So the company may take steps to find out and cater the needs of employees.

CONCLUSION

A survey on satisfaction of employees’ has been conducted to know the existing levels of satisfaction so that steps can be taken to maintain and improve the levels and to have a positive attitude among the employees towards their work.

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